

Effect of Substitution on the Stabilities of Palladium (II) Chelates of Hydroxytriazenes

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The effect of substituting -Cl, -Br, -CH₃, -NHCOCH₃, -COOH, -COCH₃, -OCH₃, and -SO₃ groups on the molecule of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene upon the stabilities of palladium chelates of substituted hydroxytriazenes has been discussed. An attempt has been made to correlate the pK_a values of ligands with the first step and overall stability constants of palladium chelates formed by them.

Hydroxytriazenes, possessing common functional grouping -N(OH)-N=N-, have recently been introduced by Sogani *et al.*¹ as a very useful class of chelating agents. Substitution of various groups at different positions of the aryl nuclei of the parent compound, 3-hydroxy-1, 3-diphenyltriazene, influenced the stability of the resulting metal chelates. The present investigation deals with the effect of substituents in the hydroxytriazene molecule on the stabilities of palladium (II) chelates corresponding to the compositions 1 : 1 and 1 : 2. An attempt has also been made to correlate the pK_a values of ligands with the first step and the overall stability constants of their chelates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydroxytriazenes were prepared by adopting the method given by Sogani *et al.*¹. Dissociation quotients of hydroxytriazenes could not be determined by conventional potentiometric and conductometric methods because of their weak acidic nature. So pK_a values of these compounds were determined spectrophotometrically by the authors² using Robinson's method.

Bjerrum-Calvin's method³ was adopted for the measurement of the stability constants of metal chelates. The solution in 70% dioxan-water was 0.1M, 0.0002M, 0.008M with respect to potassium chloride, metal ions, and the ligand, respectively and with sufficient amount of nitric acid to lower the pH to about 2. Cambridge bench type pH meter was used to follow the changes in pH during the titration with 0.02M sodium hydroxide at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The electrode system consisted of a glass (pH range 1-13) and a saturated calomel electrode as reference. Stability constants of palladium chelates and pK_a values of the ligands are summarised in Table I. The experimental error is ± 0.02 .

DISCUSSION

Effect of substitution on stabilities of chelates : The stabilities of palladium chelates of various hydroxytriazenes have been given in Table I.

1. N. C. Sogani and S. C. Bhattacharya, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 81, 1616; *Idem.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 563; T. C. Jain, H. K. L. Gupta and N. C. Sogani, *ibid.*, 1960, **37**, 531; H. K. L. Gupta and N. C. Sogani, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 771.
2. D. N. Purohit and N. C. Sogani, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964 (8), 2820.
3. M. Calvin and N. C. Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.

TABLE I

S.No.	Compound			pK_a^*	$\log k_1$	$\log k_2$	$\log k_1 k_2$ ($\log K$)
	R	R'	R''				
1.	H	H	H	11.41	11.57	11.09	22.66
2.	Cl	H	H	10.72	10.70	10.25	20.95
3.	H	Cl	H	10.52	10.43	10.00	20.43
4.	H	H	Cl	10.65	10.56	10.12	20.68
5.	Br	H	H	10.86	10.86	10.44	21.30
6.	CH ₃	H	H	11.78	11.89	11.46	23.35
7.	H	CH ₃	H	11.55	11.70	11.27	22.97
8.	H	H	CH ₃	11.86	12.01	11.53	23.54
9.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	12.18	12.33	11.90	22.23
10.	NHCOCH ₃	H	H	11.66	11.82	11.39	22.21
11.	COOH	H	H	10.97	11.33	10.90	22.23
12.	COCH ₃	H	H	10.96	10.97	10.54	21.51
13.	OCH ₃	H	H	11.95	12.06	11.68	23.74
14.	SO ₃ ⁻	H	H	9.99	9.71	9.32	19.03

* Ref. 2.

A comparison of the value of overall stability constants of methyl substituted hydroxytriazene palladium chelates with that of parent hydroxytriazene chelate reveals that methyl group at position 4 on ring B (I; R = CH₃, R' = R'' = H) increases the overall stability of chelates. The hydroxytriazene with methyl group at position 4' on ring A (I; R = R' = H, R'' = CH₃) forms palladium chelates of still greater stability. This is because +I effect (electron pushing) of methyl group is dominant on the -OH bearing nitrogen atom from ring A than that from ring B due to distance factor. The still greater stability of palladium chelate of 4, 4'-dimethyl substituted hydroxytriazene (I; R = CH₃, R' = H, R'' = CH₃) than either of the monomethyl isomers is quite reasonable in view of the arguments given above.

The chloro and bromo substituted hydroxytriazenes are more acidic and form less stable chelates as compared to the parent compound. It has been observed that hydroxytriazene with bromine at position 4 on ring B (I; R = Br, R' = R'' = H), forms more stable chelate than that of the compound with chlorine at the same position (I; R = Cl, R' = R'' = H), which in turn forms chelates of greater stability than that of hydroxytriazene in which chlorine is at position 4' on ring A (I; R = R' = H, R'' = Cl). This seems to be quite reasonable in view of the fact that the inductive effect of halogens decreases in the order F > Cl > Br > I. It is apparent that the +M effect of the chlorine is not operative in these compounds owing to the strong +M effect on -N = N- group and only the -I effect of halogens is affecting the acidity of the hydroxytriazenes and the stability of their palladium chelates.

The hydroxytriazene with a methyl group at position—2 on ring B (I; $R = R'' = H$, $R' = CH_3$) should have been a weaker acid and formed more stable chelate than its para-isomer owing to the nearness of the +I effect of the group on -OH bearing nitrogen atom. However, contrary is the case. The greater acidity and less stability of chelates of ortho- than the para- isomer is due to the ortho- effect of methyl group. The strong acidity and small stability of palladium chelate of 2 chloro substituted hydroxytriazene (I; $R = R'' = H$, $R' = Cl$) may be due to the proximity of -I effect of Cl; and to the inhibition of hydrogen bonding or metal chelate ring by virtue of the ortho-effect of the halogen.

Both the 4 acetamido and 4 methoxy substituted hydroxytriazenes (ring B : I; $R' = R'' = H$, $R = NHCOCH_3$ and OCH_3 respectively) are less acidic and form more stable chelates than the parent hydroxytriazene. This may be attributed to the +M effect of $-NHCOCH_3$ and $-OCH_3$ group.

The strong acid character of the hydroxytriazenes with substitution of $-SO_3Na$, $-COOH$, and $-COCH_3$ groups at position 4 on ring B (I; $R' = R'' = H$, $R = SO_3Na$, $COOH$ and $COCH_3$ respectively), and smaller stability of their palladium chelates is due to the -M effect of these groups. The stabilities of these hydroxytriazenes chelates are increasing

Fig 1 Relation between pK 's of ligands/ k_1 and k_2 of Palladium chelates

as the -M effect of the groups decreases. In the case of 4-COOH substituted hydroxytriazene (ring B : I; $R' = R'' = H$, $R = COOH$), it seems that the pK_a (-OH) value and the values of stability constants of palladium chelates are slightly higher. This is due to the fact that the compound has two dissociation constants, the first being due to the ionisation of carboxyl group $pK(COOH) = 6.32$ and the second to the ionisation of -OH group ($pK_{OH} = 10.97$). The removal of a proton from a negative ion is difficult, hence the pK_{OH} value of the compound is slightly high.

Relation between dissociation quotients of hydroxytriazenes and stability constants of palladium chelates : An attempt has been made to study the relation between the acid dissociation constants (pK_a) of different hydroxytriazenes and the first step ($\log k_1$) and the overall stability ($\log K$) constants of the palladium chelates. The results are given in Fig. 1. The numerals locating the points in the figures correspond to the serial number of hydroxytriazenes given in the Table 1. It will be seen that most of the points lie on straight line, or within the limit of experimental error, excepting for 4-carboxy (Sl. No. 11) and 4-sulphonate (Sl. No. 14) derivatives of hydroxytriazines. It seems that the pK_a values of these compounds are slightly higher than expected owing to the involvement of removal of a proton from a neutral molecule as in the remaining triazenes. Hence, these hydroxytriazenes are expected to behave in a slightly different way than the remaining compounds.

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